

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE HAJJ PILGRIM PROTECTION POLICY WEST JAVA PROVINCE AT THE BEKASI HAJJ DORMITORY (STUDY ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE HAJJ PILGRIMAGE IN 2023 - 2025)

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Abstract

The weak enforcement of area order, the regulation of pilgrims entering/exiting the area, and the supervision of pilgrims' belongings, as mandated in Law Number 8 of 2019 concerning Hajj and Umrah Organization, indicates that the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory has not been optimal. This research aims to explore the factors contributing to the non-optimal implementation of the protection policy for Hajj pilgrims from West Java Province at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory and to formulate strategies for optimizing the implementation of the Hajj Pilgrim protection policy for West Java Province at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. The research was conducted using a qualitative approach and a case study method on the Hajj implementation in 2023 – 2025 at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. Data collection was carried out through in-depth interviews with 12 key informants from the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory; Class I Health Quarantine Center Bandung; Bekasi City Resort Police; Bekasi City Ministry of Religious Affairs; Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Cooperative; Hajj Pilgrims from West Java Province for the years 2023 – 2025; and document review. The results show that the factors causing the non-optimal implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy for West Java Province at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory are: (1) availability of regulations, (2) availability of resources, (3) attitude of implementers, (4) policy communication, (5) implementation coordination, and (6) the attitude of the Hajj pilgrims. Five strategies were formulated to make the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy for West Java Province at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory more optimal based on the analysis results: (1) establishing a Pos Silaturahmi (Friendship Post), (2) regulating seasonal workers, (3) increasing the frequency of message delivery, (4) adding CCTV cameras, and (5) installing a CCTV monitor at the Security Post.

Keywords: Policy Implementation, Hajj Pilgrims, Bekasi Hajj Dormitory

INTRODUCTION

Organizing the Hajj pilgrimage is a global religious activity with the main challenge of maintaining the safety and managing the movement of millions of pilgrims in a short time in a limited area. (Al-Thaqafi, 2025) The safety of pilgrims is a priority that requires careful planning, solid coordination, and the support of technology and other services. Several countries with large Muslim populations have developed security protection systems. In Pakistan, the "Pak Hajj 2025" mobile application was launched to guide and facilitate pilgrims with features such as Hajj training schedules, flight details, and navigation assistance designed to help pilgrims navigate the busy routes and important locations during the Hajj. (Khurram, 2025) The Bangladesh government is enhancing monitoring and support for Hajj pilgrims in Saudi Arabia by establishing Hajj Management Centers in Ashkona, Makkah, and Madinah and introducing a mobile application that provides lost property tracking, medical assistance, complaint handling, and real-time information. (Habib, 2025). Implementation of security for Malaysian Hajj pilgrims is carried out through coordination meetings between Tabung Haji and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, followed by provision of preparatory courses for officers and Hajj rituals for pilgrims before leaving for the Holy Land (Fadli, 2024). Indonesia, as the world's largest hajj-sending country, is also striving to strengthen its protection system for pilgrims through Law Number 8 of 2019 concerning the Implementation of the Hajj and Umrah Pilgrimages. Protection for pilgrims includes protection as Indonesian citizens, legal protection, security protection, and protection against life, accidents, and health. This protection begins when pilgrims enter the hajj dormitory for departure and ends when they

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leave the dormitory for their return. The Bekasi Hajj Dormitory plays a strategic role as the starting and ending point for Hajj pilgrim protection, serving as an extension of the International Airport and a series of CIQ (Customs, Immigration, and Quarantine) activities. In accordance with Government Regulation Number 8 of 2022, Article 24, paragraph (5), security protection at the Hajj Dormitory includes securing belongings, physical protection, and guaranteeing personal safety.

West Java Province consistently contributes the largest number of Hajj pilgrims in Indonesia. Based on Decree of the Minister of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia No. 1196 of 2024,(2024)The quota will reach 38,230 people in 2025 (36,295 regular pilgrims and 1,935 seniors). In line with the national theme of Elderly and Disability-Friendly Hajj,(Azhar, 2024) (Vitiara, 2024),The high number of pilgrims, especially the elderly, demands that the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory be prepared to guarantee security. The Bekasi Hajj Dormitory implements a ring system as a security management mechanism with different levels of access. RING-I is a sterile area that can only be entered by officers and pilgrims with special permission. RING-II is a restricted area for pilgrims to rest, with no access for escorts or partners. RING-III has limited access for service activities, including the sale of pilgrims' needs by partners. RING-IV is the area with the most relaxed access for escorts and outside parties, as per regulations. This ring division is used to maintain order and security during Hajj operations.

Table 1.1Division of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Area

No	Area	Location Description
1	RING-I	Forbidden Area (Sterile), Muzdalifah Hall Boarding Area, yard and parking area for the departure of the pilgrim's bus
2	RING-II	Restricted Area of Muzdalifah Building, Mina A, B, C, D and E which is used for Hajj pilgrims to rest
3	RING-III	Front yard of the Main Building
4	RING-IV	In front of the Hajj Dormitory gate and outside rear parking

Source:Security Report on the Departure and Return Activities of PPIH Embarkation-Debarcation Jakarta-Bekasi 2024(2024)

Figure 1.1Hajj Dormitory Area Division Plan for Bekasi

Source:Processed by Researchers, 2025

However, the implementation of security protection policies at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory during the 2023–2025 period is considered less than optimal. This is evident from three main issues: First, weak implementation of maintaining order in the area, marked by the discovery of illegal money exchange practices by officers of the Hajj and Umrah Guidance Group (KBIHU) in the Limited Area (Ring II), as well as escorts of pilgrims entering and gathering in the Sterile Area (Ring I) and the Lodging Area (Ring II). Second, the ineffective regulation of pilgrims leaving/entering the Hajj Dormitory Area, as seen from pilgrims still leaving to consume food from the canteen that does not meet the health recommendations of the Hajj Organizing Committee (PPIH) for Health and to receive

visitors, even though PPIH recommends restricting access to control health risks. Third, suboptimal supervision of luggage, evidenced by the occurrence of cases of lost mobile phones in 2023 and repeated in 2024 (PPIH Security Sector Evaluation Report of West Java Province 2020).(2023)And(2024)). Based on the problems that emerged, the identification of the problems refers to the less than optimal (1) maintenance of order in the area, (2) regulation of the entry/exit of pilgrims, and (3) supervision of pilgrims' belongings. Thus, this study aims to explore the factors that contribute to the less than optimal implementation of the West Java Province Hajj Pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory and to formulate strategies to optimize the implementation of the West Java Province Hajj Pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on the protection of Hajj pilgrims has been conducted using various approaches and focus areas. In general, these studies can be grouped into five main aspects: (1) regulatory and institutional aspects, (2) service standards and service management, (3) legal and consumer protection, (4) health and risk protection, and (5) operational security and food safety. A summary is presented below.

1. Regulatory and Institutional Aspects

Riyadi et al.(2023)analyzed the management of the Hajj pilgrimage based on Law No. 13 of 2008 and highlighted the protection of pilgrims through security measures and the safeguarding of their belongings. Their findings revealed weaknesses in governance, clarity of institutional functions, and infrastructure.

2. Service Standards and Service Management

Rijkiyah(2020)evaluated the implementation of Minimum Service Standards (SPM) at the Ministry of Religious Affairs in Samarinda City. The results showed that services met standards, but technical obstacles remained, particularly for elderly congregants and inclusive services.(2015)reviewed the service management of the Jakarta Embarkation Hajj Dormitory and identified that security protection was running well through the division of roles between internal officers and external officers.

3. Legal and Consumer Protection

Prabowo(2014)assessing legal protection for Hajj pilgrims from a consumer protection perspective, he found that legal protection mechanisms were suboptimal, particularly in the areas of complaints, education, and oversight of organizers.

4. Health Protection

Sagala(2007)analyzing health risk factors for pilgrims and preventive-curative interventions, especially health checks at embarkation as a form of vital protection.

5. Security Protection

Khorunnisa(2023)found that the protection of pilgrims at the Donohudan Embarkation had been carried out according to SOP, although health risks for the elderly and cases of exchanged items still occurred.

The protection of Hajj pilgrims is regulated through several policies. Law Number 8 of 2019 stipulates that the government is obliged to provide legal, security, health, and safety protection from the time pilgrims enter until they leave the Hajj dormitory. Government Regulation Number 8 of 2022 strengthens this provision by establishing four aspects of protection: protection of Indonesian citizens abroad, legal protection, security protection, and health protection. Security protection emphasizes collaboration with PPIH Embarkation elements, the Indonesian National Armed Forces (TNI), and the Indonesian National Police (Polri) in establishing an integrated security system (LINJAM) during the departure and return phases of Hajj pilgrims. PMA Number 44 of 2014 establishes the strategic role of the Hajj Dormitory as the starting and ending point for pilgrims' movements, functioning as a transit center, inspection center, final guidance center, and preparation for pilgrims' departure to Saudi Arabia.

In this study, policy implementation is understood as the process of implementing government decisions into action. The Van Meter and Van Horn model(1975) explains six factors that influence implementation, namely the clarity of policy measures and objectives, the availability of resources, the characteristics of implementing agents, the attitudes or dispositions of implementers, communication and coordination between organizations, and the economic, social, and political environmental conditions. Meanwhile, Edwards III(1980)emphasizes four key variables that determine the success of implementation, namely communication, resources, implementer disposition, and bureaucratic structure. Grindle(1980)views implementation as a political and administrative process that is assessed through two aspects, namely the suitability of the implementation process with the policy design and the achievement of predetermined objectives. Based on several theories from experts and research related to the implementation of the protection of Hajj pilgrims mentioned above, researchers have grouped the factors that contribute to the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy in West Java Province at the Bekasi Hajj

Dormitory are: (1) Availability of regulations, (2) Availability of resources, (3) Attitude of implementers, (4) Policy communication, and (5) Coordination of implementation.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method with the aim of exploring in depth the implementation of the West Java Province Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory in 2023 - 2025. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews with 12 key informants from the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory; BKK Class I Bandung; Bekasi City Police; Bekasi City Ministry of Religious Affairs; Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Cooperative; West Java Province Hajj pilgrims in 2023 - 2025 and document review. The selection of key informants was carried out selectively by considering the following criteria: (1) knowing and having the required data/information about the protection of Hajj pilgrims, (2) being directly involved in the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory and (3) having the status of stakeholders who have roles and authorities related to the Hajj pilgrim protection policy. After the data collection stage is complete, the next step is data processing and analysis. Data processing according to Miles and Huberman (2014) carried out in three stages, namely: (1) Data Condensation, (2) Data Presentation, and (3) Drawing and verifying conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the research results and discussion regarding the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. Based on the research findings, the implementation of pilgrim security protection in the 2023–2025 period is considered less than optimal, especially in maintaining order in the Hajj Dormitory area, regulating pilgrims' entry and exit, and maintaining the security of pilgrims' belongings while inside the dormitory. This discussion includes an in-depth analysis of the factors influencing the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, which includes the availability of regulations, the availability of resources, the attitudes of implementers, policy communication, and coordination of implementation as well as other factors obtained by researchers during data collection.

1. Availability of Regulations

The research results show that the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory has relatively comprehensive security guidelines and SOPs, including the 2023 Hajj Dormitory Management Guidelines and Security SOPs. However, clarity of procedures for pilgrims is still lacking due to the lack of written guidelines from the Ministry of Religious Affairs or the District/City Health Office. Procedures are only conveyed verbally during the manasik (practice) and reception of pilgrims at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Reception Hall, resulting in a gap in understanding, especially among elderly pilgrims in the context of Elderly-Friendly Hajj. From the aspect of regulatory consistency, inconsistencies were found regarding exceptions for visits by officials and the relationship between PPIH and KBIH. Meanwhile, regulatory evaluation has been ongoing, reflected in the implementation of the One Stop Service (OSS) system and improvements to canteen facilities that support food safety.

2. Resource Availability

The research results indicate that officer availability is suboptimal, primarily due to the excessive but inefficient number of external officers from the Community Order and Order (Pokdar Kamtibmas) and minimal security in confined areas. In terms of competency, many security officers lack security guard certification and have not received the latest training; some were last trained in 2005. Implementers are also suboptimal in identifying entry points and do not systematically record visitor data. For supporting facilities, additional CCTV is needed to monitor the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory area and CCTV monitors are not placed at the Security Post. The budget is considered adequate because it has been planned in the annual budget cycle.

3. Implementer's Attitude

The results of the study indicate that compliance among implementers is generally good, but there are still violations by seasonal workers and excessive discretion in restricting access to sterile areas. In terms of commitment, the signing of an integrity pact demonstrates formal commitment, but external implementers have not been consistently present. The Hajj Dormitory Cooperative demonstrated a commitment to food safety through an MoU with canteen vendors. Implementer motivation is relatively high because service to the congregation is seen as an act of worship in serving the Guests of God, although forms of appreciation are still non-material and are given through post-operational evaluation activities.

4. Policy Communication

Research shows that communication media at the executive level have been functioning through coordination meetings, WhatsApp groups, and HT, but communication with the congregation is still limited to verbal communication in the Arafah Hall and banners in the dormitory area. The frequency of message delivery to the congregation is more often done during manasik in the regions, while the delivery at the Hajj Dormitory is less effective due to the large hall conditions and the uncondusive situation and is only delivered once during the reception of the pilgrims. In terms of completeness of information, regular roll calls and cross-sector coordination are quite supportive, but there is no clear written communication channel available for the congregation.

5. Implementation Coordination

The research results show that the division of tasks between PPIH divisions is quite clear because it is based on PPIH guidelines and the division of work positions for PPIH implementers in the security sector. A shared commitment was also established through leadership meetings and the principle of equal roles between agencies "Not Discriminating by Color of Clothes" in serving the congregation. Coordination forums operate through technical meetings and WhatsApp groups, allowing for a rapid response to operational issues. In terms of conflict resolution cooperation, coordination between internal and external security, and other divisions is relatively good, particularly in handling cases of food loss and safety. However, weaknesses remain, such as imbalanced workloads and the need to strengthen the role of security in canteen supervision.

6. Attitude of the Congregation

The research results indicate that pilgrim attitudes are an additional factor contributing to the suboptimal implementation of pilgrim protection at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory. Pilgrims' awareness of their belongings remains low, as evidenced by their habit of storing items in unsafe places, which increases the risk of loss. Furthermore, compliance with quarantine regulations and access restrictions is suboptimal, as some pilgrims continue to meet with family or consume food outside of official catering outlets despite being aware of the restrictions.

Based on the research results, a strategy can be formulated to optimize the implementation of the West Java Province Hajj Congregation protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, as follows:

1. Establishment of a Silaturahmi Post

The reality on the ground shows that pilgrims are still leaving their accommodation areas and receiving family visits, despite quarantine regulations prohibiting this. This situation is also exacerbated by the fact that the meeting place for pilgrims has been shifted to the canteen, while the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory canteen is not recommended for consumption by pilgrims and has not received food sanitation approval from the PPIH Health Sector. The establishment of the Silaturahmi Post is a solution to maintain controlled meetings through determining a special location, health screening for guests wishing to visit, inspection of food brought by guests, visitor data collection, and regulating the duration of visits. This recommendation aligns with the results of the 1446H/2025M Hajj evaluation from the Inspectorate General of the Indonesian Ministry of Religious Affairs, which encourages the provision of official gathering points for pilgrims. With the Silaturahmi Post, potential security and health risks can be minimized while reducing the practice of using officer discretion.

2. Seasonal Labor Arrangement (Temus)

Seasonal workers are a vulnerable point because the recruitment process does not go through formal selection, the number is disproportionate, and there are no clear written sanctions regulations. Arrangements need to be made through: (a) open recruitment announced through the official social media of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory and competency selection according to needs; (b) adjustments to the number of meetings are also needed based on a needs analysis, considering the significant decrease in the number of pilgrims at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory in 2026. In 2026, based on the Decree of the Minister of Hajj and Umrah of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2025 concerning the Regular Hajj Quota for 1447 H/2026 AD(2025), the West Java pilgrim quota dropped to 29,643 people. With the composition of pilgrim placement at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory of 11,662 pilgrims and the Kertajati Hajj Dormitory of 17,981 pilgrims. The decrease in the number of pilgrims at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory was quite significant in 2026 compared to 2025 (from 26,620 to 11,662 pilgrims), so it must be followed by adjustments to seasonal workforce needs; and (c) the formation of written regulations containing rights, obligations, and disciplinary sanctions so that enforcement of the rules is stronger.

3. Increased Frequency of Message Delivery

The message of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy has been delivered once during the pilgrim reception process at the Arafah Hall, making it less effective for pilgrims who are focused on preparing their reception documents and the large condition of the Hall so that the message is not conveyed clearly. Repetition of information can be done through two internal media: (a) a paging system, through which a prohibition on receiving guests, a prohibition on consuming outside food, and security advice can be conveyed, especially during critical hours; and (b) an in-house channel, by adding videos containing messages of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy through televisions at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory, both in the pilgrim's rooms, lobby and dining room, as well as in strategic areas such as the hall and mosque. Repeated delivery will strengthen the understanding of pilgrims, especially the elderly.

4. Adding CCTV Cameras to Risky Areas

The availability of CCTV cameras at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory is still very limited and does not yet cover high-risk areas. Currently, CCTV installations are limited to public areas such as the hall, lobby, and several outdoor locations. Meanwhile, the corridors of the accommodation, where reports of lost belongings are most frequently reported, still lack an adequate surveillance system. With the dormitory's capacity consisting of six accommodation buildings with a capacity of 1,535 pilgrims, two halls, and one office area, only 25 CCTV cameras are available, eight of which are damaged. This surveillance coverage is not commensurate with the size of the area that must be secured, especially during the high-mobility Hajj operational period. Gradual addition of CCTV cameras is needed to increase surveillance coverage, along with repairs to damaged units.

5. Placement of CCTV Monitors at Security Posts

Currently, CCTV monitors are only located at the reception, thus not supporting real-time monitoring by security officers. Placing monitors at the security post is standard in security systems (ISO 9001, ISO 45001, and three-star hotel standards). Moving the monitors to the security post will accelerate incident response and reduce the risk of security breaches.

SUGGESTION

Based on the results of the discussion above, the following are suggestions for improvements that can be considered to optimize the implementation of the Hajj pilgrim protection policy at the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory.

1. Parties involved and contributions required

- a. The Head of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory: establishes internal policies regarding quarantine patterns, guest restrictions, and enforces sterile area regulations. Efforts to add CCTV cameras and install CCTV monitors at security posts require resource support, including budget, equipment, and competent personnel to monitor and maintain the equipment.
- b. Head of PPIH Security and Health: Develops SOPs or regulations that include, among other things, conditions for permitted visits, visitor data collection, health screening, items brought in, and meeting duration. This ensures that quarantine measures are maintained.
- c. Head of the Administration and Finance Sub-Section of the Bekasi Hajj Dormitory: in arranging seasonal workers, regulations are needed regarding recruitment that is in accordance with competencies and needs, as well as policies regarding disciplinary rules for seasonal workers.
- d. Bekasi Hajj Dormitory Staffing: conducting recruitment processes according to competency and needs and enforcing disciplinary rules.
- e. Public Relations and Receptionist: providing content containing policy messages delivered and communication media, namely loudspeakers and TV in the congregation gathering area at the Hajj Dormitory.
- f. KBIH and congregation families: comply with visiting rules at the Silaturahmi Post

2. Mechanisms to ensure strategies are implemented as planned

Each strategy needs to be outlined in an action plan that includes targets, performance indicators, responsible parties, workflows, and implementation timelines. This action plan document serves as a reference for all implementers to ensure activities proceed according to the initial plan.

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